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BASIC METHODS FOR PROTECTING THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT FROM TRAFFIC NOISE

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Annotation

The article discusses the main sources of urban noise and their impact on the noise regime of urban development, as well as urban planning means to protect against external noise. Methods for calculating noise reduction in urban areas are given; provides some information about acoustics, physical and physiological characteristics of noise and regulatory requirements. The material presented in the article is a generalization of domestic and foreign experience in noise protection in urban planning and includes the results of scientific research.

Keywords: *environment, acoustic pollution, noise, urban environment, vehicles, city master plan*

In recent decades, developed and developing countries have experienced rapid growth in the number of road transport. On the one hand, this phenomenon contributed to the rapid global economic development, and, on the other hand, it was accompanied by such negative consequences as traffic congestion, traffic accidents, air pollution, noise, and an increase in greenhouse gas emissions. The negative consequences caused by the ever-increasing amount of transport affect not only the users of vehicles, but also directly on every person on our planet.

Traffic noise is increasingly seen as a major threat to human health. The World Health Organization recognizes general noise, including traffic noise, as one of the acute problems facing humanity at this stage in the development of civilization.

Car noise at night is just as dangerous as daytime noise. Some population groups are more vulnerable to noise exposure. Since children need to sleep longer than adults, the problem of exposure to night noise is more acute for them. The chronically ill and the elderly are more sensitive to noise exposure. In addition, less affluent people who cannot afford to live in quiet neighborhoods or in sound-insulated homes tend to suffer more from the problem of excessive acoustic pollution. The noise of cars can cause a significant deterioration in both the moral and physical condition of a person. Noise not

only violates the psychological comfort of a person, but also negatively affects the performance of adults and the academic performance of children, causes sleep disturbance, affects the growth of nervous disorders and diseases of the hearing aid. So, according to the World Health Organization, with regular exposure to noise at a level of more than 80 dBA, we enter the zone of possible irreversible hearing changes.

Urban noise is an objective problem for all megacities, requiring comprehensive measures aimed at its regulation. We are talking not only about the protection of residential premises, which is solved by installing noise-protective double-glazed windows, but also about the protection of large urban areas. Sanitary norms and rules, dated 19.06.2009 No. 0267-09 "On ensuring permissible noise in the premises of residential, public buildings and on the territory of residential development", permissible noise levels are established in front of the facades of residential buildings of the first development front $LA_{eq} = 55$ dBA - during the day and no more than $LA_{eq} = 45$ dBA - at night, and in the premises of residential buildings, $LA_{eq\text{ pom}} = 40$ dBA - during the day and $LA_{eq\text{ pom}} = 30$ dBA at night. In the countries of the European Union, there are a number of policy documents that have identified noise pollution in cities as one of the main problems of negative human impact.

Noise control requires significant material costs. In European countries, about 1% of GDP is spent on it. But according to research by British experts, last year 101,000 people died from coronary diseases in Europe. Of these, about three thousand fell victim to constant noise exposure, especially from road transport.

Scientists have shown how noise affects the body. It turned out that it increases the blood levels of such stress hormones as cortisol, adrenaline and norepinephrine. Severe stress can cause heart failure, angina, high blood pressure and immune problems.

University College London professor Deepak Prasher said: "New research shows there is a link between noise and early deaths. Until recently, people did not realize the negative impact that it has on their health. All this goes unnoticed".

In addition to well-known noise-reducing measures, such as installing noise barriers along highways, installing noise-protective glazing in residential buildings, limiting the speed of vehicles in residential areas, restriction of construction work and air travel at night, in a number of countries such interesting, in our opinion, measures are being taken as subsidizing the introduction of low-noise car engines, building roads outside residential areas, using special car tires, operating less noisy aircraft, conducting video surveillance of production construction works, noise restrictions for mass sports and entertainment events, etc.

Many city and suburban arterial streets in Germany have signs with speed limits of 60 km/h, where you can drive 80-90 km/h. Under these signs is a sign explaining the reason for this restriction - noise control. Wheels that roll on asphalt at a speed of 90 km/h really make a lot more noise than at a speed of 60 km/h. And generally speaking, there are many streets in Berlin where the speed limit of 30 km / h is only valid at night, usually from 10 pm to 6 am, when residents of nearby houses are sleeping.

Protection from noise - one of the main adverse factors of the human environment - has become an integral part of

the design, construction and reconstruction of modern cities.

The growth of noise in the urban area, created by car flows, largely depends on the principles of traffic organization and the technical characteristics of vehicles: engine power and design, load capacity, speed, traffic intensity in general, the design and condition of the roadway, slopes of streets and roads, number of road crossing levels. Individual vehicles are presented as point sources of noise (if individual vehicles are considered), and traffic flows as a linear or intermittent source of noise.

In order to reduce the noise of the running gear on vehicles with internal combustion engines, air intake and exhaust mufflers are installed. The muffler of aerodynamic noise of an exhaust - the main means of protection against automobile noise. When the combustion products exit the cylinders, the exhaust gases have a speed of 500 - 600 m/s, and a temperature of over 1200 ° C, sound pressure up to 160 dB at the inlet to the muffler, these values decrease to 60 - 100 m / s, 600 ° C 120 dB, respectively.

The solution of transport problems in urban planning is associated with the development of intercity, intracity and suburban transport of all types. At the same time, the importance of solving environmental and hygienic problems associated with the adverse impact of transport on the environment is increasing.

Purpose of the article. Give a description and characterize the main methods of protecting humans and the environment from road transport noise used in modern urban planning practice.

Measures to combat urban noise can be divided into two groups: architectural and planning and construction and acoustic. Along with the development of measures to reduce the noise of transport sources, the problem of combating the noise that these sources spread into the environment arises. This problem is solved in two ways: by planning general urban planning activities in the process of drawing up master plans for cities, projects for detailed planning of

residential areas and micro districts, as well as by developing special noise protection devices that isolate, absorb and reflect noise.

Various administrative measures may be used. These include: redistribution of traffic flows by city streets; restriction of movement at different times of the day in one direction or another; change in the composition of vehicles (for example, a ban on the use of trucks and buses with diesel engines on some streets of the city), etc.

When developing city planning and development projects, both natural conditions (terrain relief and green spaces) and special structures (screens near highways) can be used to protect against noise. You can also apply rational methods of zoning the territory according to the conditions of the noise regime for certain types of buildings, plots and sites for recreation, household needs, etc.

Consider possible options for noise protection in cities. First of all, in order to protect against noise in the design of cities and other settlements, it is necessary to clearly divide the territory according to its functional use into zones: residential, industrial (industrial), communal storage and external transport. Industrial (manufacturing) and communal storage areas, designed for large cargo flows along transport routes, are located so that they do not cross the residential area and do not wedged into it. To protect against noise, when designing an external transport system, it is necessary to provide bypass railway lines in cities (to pass transit trains outside the city), locate marshalling yards outside populated areas, and technical stations and parks of reserve rolling stock, railway lines for freight traffic and access roads - outside the residential area; to separate new railway lines and stations during new construction from the residential development of cities and other settlements of the SPZ; observe the proper distance from the boundaries of airports, factory, military airfields to the boundaries of residential development. The width of the SPZ must be justified by acoustic calculations and sanitary standards regulated by ShNK 2.07.01-03* "Urban planning. Planning for the

development and development of the territories of urban and rural settlements" and KMK 2.01.08-2019. "Noise Protection".

When laying new or reconstructing main streets and roads in a residential area, it is necessary to provide for measures to protect against traffic noise, justified by acoustic calculations. High-speed roads and citywide roads with predominantly freight transport should not cross the residential area. In residential areas, the laying of high-speed roads, with appropriate justification, is allowed in tunnels or excavations. Rational bypass roads that direct transit flows outside the city.

Terrain elements should be used as natural barriers to noise propagation. If it is necessary to lay main streets and roads on embankments and overpasses, install noise protective screens.

When designing a street and road network, the maximum possible enlargement of inter-main territories, a decrease in the number of intersections and other transport hubs, and the installation of smooth curvilinear road connections should be provided. It is necessary to limit through traffic in residential areas.

In the architectural and planning structure of residential areas and microdistricts, the following methods of noise protection are used: removal of residential buildings from noise sources; location between noise sources and residential buildings-screens; the use of rational, from the point of view of noise protection, composite methods for grouping residential buildings.

Functional zoning of the territories of microdistricts should be carried out taking into account the need to place residential buildings and preschool institutions in areas most remote from noise sources, highways, parking lots, garages, transformer substations, etc. In areas adjacent to noise sources, it is possible to build buildings that allow higher sound levels. These are consumer services, trade, catering, utilities, administrative and public institutions. Shopping centers and service blocks are usually built on the border of microdistricts

along transport routes in the form of a single complex.

If residential development needs to be placed on the border of microdistricts along transport routes, it is advisable to use special types of noise-protected residential buildings. Depending on the conditions of insolation, it is recommended to build: noise-protected residential buildings, the architectural and planning solutions of which are characterized by the orientation towards noise sources of the windows of auxiliary premises and no more than one living room without sleeping places in multi-room apartments; noise protected residential buildings with increased soundproofing properties of external building envelopes oriented towards noise sources and with built-in supply ventilation systems.

To ensure sanitary standards in apartments and on the territory of microdistricts, it is necessary to use compositional techniques for grouping the noise of protected buildings, based on the creation of a closed space. When residential buildings are located along highways, one should not resort to compositional methods of grouping residential buildings, which are based on the disclosure of space towards the roadway.

If architectural and planning measures (breaks, building methods, etc.) do not provide the proper noise regime in buildings and on the territory of a residential microdistrict, and also in order to save the territory necessary to comply with territorial gaps with highways, it is advisable to use building acoustic methods: noise protection structures and devices, screens, noise protection strips of landscaping, and for residential buildings also window openings with increased sound insulation.

Various buildings and structures can be used as screens: buildings with reduced noise requirements; noise protected residential buildings; artificial or natural relief elements (cuttings, ravines, earth ramparts, embankments, mounds) and walls (roadside retaining, enclosing and noise protective). Noise protective screens should be placed as close as possible to the noise

source.

It is promising to use special types of residential buildings along highways that act as noise barriers. Such a house, as a rule, has a considerable length and can protect an entire microdistrict from noise.

Buildings with reduced noise requirements (consumer services, trade, public catering, utilities; public and cultural and educational, administrative and economic institutions) and noise-protected residential buildings should be placed along noise sources in the form of frontal, if possible continuous, development. Premises of administrative, public, cultural and educational institutions with increased requirements for acoustic comfort (conference halls, reading rooms, auditoriums of theaters, cinemas, clubs, etc.) should be built on the side opposite from noise sources. They are separated from the highway by corridors, foyers, halls, cafes and buffets, ancillary facilities.

At present, the principle of noise screening is beginning to be applied in the urban planning practice of Ukraine.

As an additional means to protect against noise, you can use special noise protective strips of green spaces. Several strips are formed with gaps between them equal to the height of the trees. The width of the strip should be at least 5 m, and the height of the trees should be at least 5 - 8 m. On the noise protection strips, the crowns of the trees should tightly close together. A dense shrub is planted under the crowns in a checkerboard pattern. Plant fast-growing, resistant species of trees and shrubs. However, the effectiveness of even special noise protection strips of green spaces is low (5 - 8 dBA).

In many cases, when buildings are located on city and regional main streets and along express roads, special noise-protected houses are erected with increased sound insulation of external fences of all rooms facing the "noisy facade". In such noise-protected buildings, used as a screen to limit the noise propagation zone deep into the residential area, a special layout of the

premises is provided, in which the bedrooms, operating rooms, wards are oriented to the facade opposite the main street.

At the stage of development of the master plan of the city, it is advisable to draw up a noise map of the road network and the largest sources of industrial noise. Noise maps are compiled on the basis of the results of field instrumental measurements in natural conditions or by calculation. The necessity and expediency of using territorial gaps, screening structures and noise protection strips of green spaces is determined by calculating the sound level at the design point on the territory of the facility that needs to be protected from noise.

In today's most common sound absorption schemes, various sound-absorbing materials and structures are used. Porous ones are popular; resonant; panel sound absorbers; combinations of the above scavengers. Known among porous absorbers are boards of felt or molded elements made from glass fibres, mineral fibers and organic fibers, as well as open-cell foams. Currently, fibrous absorbers are mainly used, since absorbers made of open-cell foam are still manufactured using a rather complex technology. However, many of the results associated with the use of fibrous materials can be extended to foam absorbers.

Conclusions. The described architectural and planning techniques for protecting the population from traffic noise show the possibility of regulating the noise level of urban areas at all stages of the design of populated areas.

Along with the planning aspects of solving the problem of protecting the urban environment from noise, an active search is being made for technical methods to reduce the negative impacts of existing modes of transport on the environment.

When developing a city master plan, the designer has the opportunity to regulate its acoustic regime by choosing the most rational transport and planning structure (or improving the existing one) in order to

overcome two main negative phenomena characteristic of modern large (largest) cities: dispersion of freight traffic and high traffic congestion. road network in the face of growing motorization. Both factors can be adjusted by improving the functional and spatial organization of the city and the formation of a promising transport network built on the principles of differentiating highways by purpose, speed and mode of transport.

To achieve maximum results in the fight against excessive noise impact of vehicles on the environment, a comprehensive, integrated approach is needed.

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